

A STUDY ON AUTOMATIC PVC PIPE CUTTING

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ABSTRACT

In the process of production of any components from steel bar stock, the preliminary process is that of cutting-of bar stock to length according to the finished size requirement of work piece. This process is normally done by an power hacksaw machine.

The sequence of operation is as follows:

1. Feed bar stock to stopper that is set according to length of work piece to be cut.
2. Clamp the bar stock.
3. Feed the cutter blade to cut the required length.
4. Retract the cutter.
5. De-clamp the work piece

....procedure repeated.

The above sequence if observed has the human intervention throughout the process is necessary and more over the process of bar cutting does not add to the value of the product hence can be treated to be an idle time. Thus there is an attempt in the form of continuous cutting off machine to reduce the idle time to a minimal value. In the machine once the bar stock is fed to the stopper the machine automatically feeds the cutter to the work piece until it is cut to the required length during the cutting stroke and during the return stroke the bar will automatically fed to the stopper by the machine itself and so also the clamping of bar stock during cutting stroke and de-clamping being by the machine itself.

KEYWORDS - Cutting , PVC, Automatic.